

Deliverable D6.3.

Pilot (IT) Technical report and achieved results (1 | 2)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BWI	Bond Work Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DDE	Dynamic Data Exchange DDE
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
DoA	Description of Action
DWH	Data Warehouse
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HMD	Hydrometallurgy Division
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTA	Key Technology Areas
LCSI	Local Crushing and Screening Interface
MAC	Measurement and Control Division
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
MPD	Mineral Processing Division
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
RCSI	Remote Crushing and Screening Interface
RP	Reporting Period
PRC	Project Research Committee
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

Pioltello quarry is Holcim's pilot site which is located in Milan area, with a crushing and screening plant for aggregates production and a dredge excavating alluvial material. The crushing and screening plant is subject to DigiEcoQuarry implementations.

As stated in Grant Agreement (GA), Pioltello pilot site is running a series of activities connected to the tasks and KPI specific for Pioltello pilot, which come from WP2 to WP5:

- High resolution models for crushing and screening optimization.
- Devices for automation of the treatment plant.
- Monitoring sensors and analysis tools for mobile machinery.
- BIM (Building Information Modelling).
- Artificial Intelligence algorithms.
- H&S technologies.
- Environmental simulation platform.

Figure 1. Drone view of Pioltello pilot site.

In detail, Pioltello site is focused on Crushing and Screening Optimization (WP2 – KTA 2.2) and on the section of Treatment and Processing relative to the aggregates production plant with the Production control system and automation and Sensors (WP3 – KTA 3.1) and on the part of Monitoring and Sensors on mobile equipment in relation to aspects of H&S and also recognition systems for workers (WP3 – KTA 3.2).

From IT point of view, Platform design has been implemented (WP4 – KTA 4.3), BIM models (WP4 – KTA 4.1) and AI algorithms for stockpile volume calculation (WP4 – KTA 4.2) as well as H&S & environmental system management (WP5 – KTA 5.1).

In addition, as group leader of WP6, Holcim has the role of coordinator of the other pilot sites, monitoring on-going activities, the respect of the timelines and organizing periodical meetings to update the progresses of the tasks.

2 Implementation of technologies

The first stage, from M1 to M13 consisted in preparing and sharing data with the other partners of the project, defining the applications and sensors to be installed on Pioltello plant.

2.1 Models for crushing and screening optimization (Task 2.7)

MINTEK's contribution to task 2.7 aims at developing breakage and screening models, obtaining online Particle Size Distribution (PSD) measurements, designing and implementing a Remote Crushing and Screening Interface (RCSI) and a Local Crushing and Screening Interface (LCSI, located at the HOLCIM site and being linked to the Data Lake and RCSI). These different components facilitate the creation of a digital twin of a crushing-screening circuit and the use of the twin for plant optimization through changes in certain operational parameters without interfering with the production of the physical plant.

MINTEK is currently executing these tasks at three of its divisions: the Mineral Processing Division (MPD), Hydrometallurgy Division (HMD) and Measurement and Control division (MAC).

2.1.1 Tasks conducted at MPD – MINTEK

Figure 2. Packaged sample material shipped from Pioltello plant to MINTEK.

HOLCIM collected samples from its quarry, stored them in bins and shipped them to MINTEK. The MPD team was responsible for the sample administration and the determination of its physical characteristics. MPD analyzed the samples for their Particle Size Distributions (PSD), Bond Work Indices (BWI) and breakage characteristics. MPD initiated this sub-task upon the delivery of the samples during late May 2022. The team carried out single-particle breakage tests on sample particles using a laboratory drop-weight tester (schematic shown in Figure 3). HMD is using the data generated to calibrate the parameters of the selected breakage distribution function ($B(x, y)$ - Equation 1).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of a typical drop weight tester.

$$B(x, y) = K \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^{n_1} + (1 - K) \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^{n_2} \quad (1)$$

The calibrated parameters in Equation 1 are:

- K – fraction of daughter particles belonging to the fine fraction.
- n_1 – fitting parameter.
- n_2 – fitting parameter.

Figure 4 shows the typical results obtained from the single-particle drop-weight tests while Figure 3 shows a sample of the breakage function parameter values obtained and their relationship with parent-particle size. MINTEK is consistently analysing both the breakage distribution function and its calibrated parameters.

Figure 4. Sample cumulative percent passing results obtained from single-particle drop-weight tests conducted on particles selected from aggregate samples sent to MINTEK by HOLCIM.

Currently, HMD is utilizing the Anderson Whiten classification function (Equations 2 to 5), along with the breakage distribution function, for the calibration and simulation of the crusher.

$$C(d_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } d_i < k_1 \\ 1 - \left(\frac{k_2 - d_i}{k_2 - k_1}\right)^{k_3} & k_1 < d_i < k_2 \\ 1 & \text{for } d_i > k_2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$k_1 = A_0 + (A_1 * CSS) - (A_2 * TPM) + (A_3 * F_{80}) + (A_4 * LLEN) \quad (3)$$

$$k_2 = B_0 + (B_1 * CSS) - (B_2 * TPM) + (B_3 * F_{80}) + (B_4 * LLEN) + (B_5 * ET) \quad (4)$$

$$P = (I - C) * (I - (B_C)^{-1}) * F \quad (5)$$

Where: A_0 to A_4 and B_0 to B_5 are calibration parameters; CSS – crusher closed size setting (mm); TPM – tons per hour throughput; $LLEN$ – length of face mantle liner (mm); LHR – liner age (hr), F_{80} – 80% passing size of feed and ET – Eccentric throw (mm).

Figure 5. Variation of breakage function parameter values (K, n1, n2) with average parent-particle size.

2.1.2 Tasks conducted at HMD - MINTEK

HMD is currently designing the RCSI that consists of a Microsoft® Excel interface with Dynamic Data Exchange (DDE) with IDEAS™ flowsheet simulator from ANDRITZ (inc.). HOLCIM shared their flowsheet with MINTEK and the red dashed line in Figure 6 bound the area of interest.

Figure 6. Part of the flowsheet of HOLCIM, with the sub-section to be simulated enclosed by red-dashed lines.

HMD has developed a flowsheet model on IDEAS™ of this sub-section shown in Figure 7. The Microsoft® Excel interface will be able to exchange data with this flowsheet model. HMD is currently automating the initially developed version of the Excel interface in order to reduce the required level of interactivity needed to obtain the relevant outputs. This will aid the MAC Division in its development of digital twin agents and data connectors. Figure 8 shows the current level of functionality of this upgraded interface. HMD is using the Visual Basic programming language and environment for this task.

Figure 7. IDEASTM flowsheet model. PD blocks display the PSD of components within the attached stream. They do not correspond to the online PSD instruments installed at HOLCIM.

Breakage Function Calibration

Screen Size	Breakage Function	Value
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	0.00
4	0.00	0.00
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	0.00
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	0.00
16	0.00	0.00
17	0.00	0.00
18	0.00	0.00
19	0.00	0.00
20	0.00	0.00
21	0.00	0.00
22	0.00	0.00
23	0.00	0.00
24	0.00	0.00
25	0.00	0.00
26	0.00	0.00
27	0.00	0.00
28	0.00	0.00
29	0.00	0.00
30	0.00	0.00
31	0.00	0.00
32	0.00	0.00

PSD Function Calibration

Screen Size	Calculated PSD	Measured PSD	Percentage Error
1	100.00	100.00	0.00
2	100.00	100.00	0.00
3	100.00	100.00	0.00
4	100.00	100.00	0.00
5	100.00	100.00	0.00
6	100.00	100.00	0.00
7	100.00	100.00	0.00
8	100.00	100.00	0.00
9	100.00	100.00	0.00
10	100.00	100.00	0.00
11	100.00	100.00	0.00
12	100.00	100.00	0.00
13	100.00	100.00	0.00
14	100.00	100.00	0.00
15	100.00	100.00	0.00
16	100.00	100.00	0.00
17	100.00	100.00	0.00
18	100.00	100.00	0.00
19	100.00	100.00	0.00
20	100.00	100.00	0.00
21	100.00	100.00	0.00
22	100.00	100.00	0.00
23	100.00	100.00	0.00
24	100.00	100.00	0.00
25	100.00	100.00	0.00
26	100.00	100.00	0.00
27	100.00	100.00	0.00
28	100.00	100.00	0.00
29	100.00	100.00	0.00
30	100.00	100.00	0.00
31	100.00	100.00	0.00
32	100.00	100.00	0.00

Breakage Matrix Generation

Screen Size	Breakage Matrix	Value
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	0.00
4	0.00	0.00
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	0.00
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	0.00
16	0.00	0.00
17	0.00	0.00
18	0.00	0.00
19	0.00	0.00
20	0.00	0.00
21	0.00	0.00
22	0.00	0.00
23	0.00	0.00
24	0.00	0.00
25	0.00	0.00
26	0.00	0.00
27	0.00	0.00
28	0.00	0.00
29	0.00	0.00
30	0.00	0.00
31	0.00	0.00
32	0.00	0.00

Classification Function Calibration

Screen Size	Classification Function	Value
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	0.00
4	0.00	0.00
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	0.00
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	0.00
16	0.00	0.00
17	0.00	0.00
18	0.00	0.00
19	0.00	0.00
20	0.00	0.00
21	0.00	0.00
22	0.00	0.00
23	0.00	0.00
24	0.00	0.00
25	0.00	0.00
26	0.00	0.00
27	0.00	0.00
28	0.00	0.00
29	0.00	0.00
30	0.00	0.00
31	0.00	0.00
32	0.00	0.00

Main Console

- Go to BF Calibration
- Go to PSD Calibration
- Go to Breakage Matrix Calibration
- Go to Classification Matrix Calibration

Figure 8. Microsoft® Excel interface developed for the calibration of flowsheet parameters. Interface performs breakage and classification function calibrations. The Swebrec PSD function is fitted to the plant PSD data.

HMD will use the online PSD data from the particle size detection sensors installed at HOLCIM, along with other relevant plant data to run multiple calibration tests to ensure that the obtained parameters are representative of the crusher operation. These parameters (breakage and classification functions) are used to simulate the crusher object in IDEAS™ which is connected to various screen objects that will also be calibrated based on plant data. Figure 9 shows an example

of the calibration results obtained using the model. MINTEK will continue discussions with HOLCIM regarding its data requirements for the optimization and further calibration of the model.

Figure 9. Sample calibration results using fitted breakage and classification function parameters. Plant Data (Swebrec) – Feed: represents the PSD data of the feed to the crusher. Plant Data (Swebrec) – Product represents the PSD data for the crusher product.

2.1.3 Tasks conducted at MAC - MINTEK

The MAC team is responsible for the LCSi development that can establish a two-way communication pathway between the pilot site and the RCSI and between the LCSi and the central Data Lake. The design of the LCSi is underway at MAC. The system design focusses on providing a generic platform that is not tied to the pilot site or the details of the Digital Twin. A micro-service-based design will be followed, allowing the individual features to be developed and extended as needed. Simulation and optimisation results can be archived in the DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) Data Lake.

The system design consists of a measurement data storage service. This service abstracts the specific details of the MAESTRO system and the LCSi, unifying data captured automatically with data captured manually. Therefore, this will provide a harmonised interface and store measurements the Digital Twin requires. A Digital Twin Calibration Service will interact with a Calibration Agent to provide calibration data, control and monitor the calibration process. The calibration record will also be stored. The Digital Twin Calibration and Simulation agent will be responsible for one or more of the digital twins. Due to the different applications, different agents may handle the calibration and simulation processes. Metadata about the digital twin will identify it uniquely in this system and store every aspect necessary to calibrate the twin and execute simulations.

The LCSi to be installed at HOLCIM will record manual measurements, trigger the recalibration of the model automatically and perform simulations to optimise the crushing circuit. The data entered here will be stored in the measurement data storage services.

A meeting and several online discussions took place between MINTEK, HOLCIM and MAESTRO staff, providing the necessary details for MINTEK to begin extracting data from the MAESTRO system. A library was developed that will form the core of the future data connector to the MAESTRO system. Libraries have been developed to support treating this data as generic measurements. A generic measurement stores one or more numerical values that are logically related, timestamped and connected to a description and unit of measurement. Generic code to export these measurements to

Excel was developed. Initially, this has been used to provide data internally for manually checking and calibration of the Digital Twin. The Digital Twin Agent will reuse this functionality to automatically interact with the Excel interface of the digital twin. Data connectors are being developed to import data from systems in use at the plant as well as export data to the Data Lake.

The goal in following the above design is to provide a system that can be re-used at other quarries and with other Digital Twins and simulation software.

2.1.4 Task conducted on Pioltello site

After the collection of the samples and the shipping to MINTEK, HOLCIM started with the installation of two PSD (Particle Size Detection) sensors for granulometry measurement has been performed on week 15-19 May from HOLCIM.

Figure 10. PSD sensor installed in the tunnel in Pioltello plant.

In the first stage, one PSD sensor has been installed inside the tunnel, which is the stockpile of material feeding the plant.

It was decided to modify the point of installation, since from that point it was not possible to link the granulometry with the crushing process, because between the PSD sensor and the crusher there is a vibrating screen which modifies the granulometry of the material.

After removing the sensor from the tunnel, one sensor has been placed on the conveyor belt before the main cone crusher, while the other was installed on the belt placed after the crusher. Thus, the two PSD sensors acquire and analyse data regarding input/output material of the main cone crusher. The sensors are running and data are ready to be transferred to Data Lake.

Together with the camera, which is the core of the vision system, also two stripes of led lights have been installed. The lights can be turned on/off from PLC, allowing to test if better results are achieved with natural or artificial lighting.

Figure 11. Q-vision sensors, supplied by MA-ESTRO for the granulometry detection of material before and after the main cone crusher.

Figure 12. Processing of the images acquired by the 2 PDS sensors for the granulometry detection.

The system gives as output data regarding the distribution of the aggregates sizes. This granulometry line can be plotted on a graph representing the cumulative percentage distribution of the material, both for natural and for crushed aggregates.

Figure 13. Plotted data of the PSD for the material before the crushing (left) and after the crushing (right).

In addition, a weigh system has been installed on the conveyor belt placed after the cone crusher (the same where one of the two PSD sensors is installed). The system has been supplied by ARCO and is described in the next chapter. It allows to acquire additional information for the creation of the crushing models.

2.2 Production control system and automation (Task 3.2)

Installations have been performed in collaboration with MAESTRO, that supplies sensors and automation. Installation phase has been concluded in June 2022. A sensor lists, positioning and status is taken under control by periodically updating the flowsheet of Pioltello plant (see Annex I).

Acquired data are processed and then accessible from MAESTRO's portal. The portal gives access to information as cumulative production volumes and production rate per aggregate type, working time (starting and arrest times), granulometry of incoming material (sensed with Q-vision system) and electrical consumption. All these data, and others, are organized in daily and annual datasheets, saved in historical reports and sent to Data Lake so that are accessible to the interested partners.

Figure 14. Synoptic picture of Pioltello plant from Maestro's portal.

Below there is a list of the sensors, what they measure and the KPIs they act on. Following, there is a brief description of each sensor type.

Table 1. List of sensors installed on Pioltello site.

Qty	Sensors	Measuring Unit	Energy	Water	Efficiency	m ³ H ₂ O/ton	kWh/ton
2	Qvision	t/h	x				x
8	Volumetric sensor	m ³ /h			x		
2	Weigh system	t/h			x		
4	Pressure transducer	bar		x		x	
1	Temperature sensor	degrees			x		
5	Vibration sensor	amplitude, frequency	x				x
4	Anti-skid sensor	i/o			x		
2	Pump liter counter	liters, m ³		x		x	
3	Camera	image			x		
10	Electric Transducer	amper	x				x
8	Anti-sticking sensor	radar			x		
2	Level sensor	% capacity			x		
27	Rotation control	pulse counter			x		
1	Power center absorption	kWh	x				x

2.2.1 Anti-skid sensors

Anti-skid sensors detect the belt slipping sideways, avoiding damaging the belt and reducing maintenance time, thus increasing efficiency. These sensors have 2 levels of warning: the first notifies if the belt is not sufficiently centered respect to roller drum, the second level warns if it has slipped till a point where it can be damaged. These sensors work in couple and are mounted one on the right and one on the left of the belt. Thank to this sensor, an alarm pops up to the plant operators noticing they have to intervene in adjusting the belt, preventing the belts from tearing off.

Figure 15. Anti-skid sensor for detection of undesired side-motion of the belt.

2.2.2 Volumetric sensors

Volumetric sensors measure incoming volumes in stockpiles. There are in total 8 volumetric sensors installed on the top of each unloading conveyor belt. They work in combination with rotation sensors, so that volumetric sensor scan the incoming material profile and rotation sensor encodes conveyor belt speed. In this way it is possible to calculate volumes that are unloaded in each stockpile, giving production volumes for each aggregate type. Instantaneous and cumulated material flows are determined and accessible from Maestro portal.

Figure 16. Volumetric sensor installed on the top of an unloading conveyor belt.

This sensor represents an innovative, and in some cases still experimental, alternative to weighbridge sensor based on loadcell. Weighbridge systems are reliable systems but their drawback is the contact between the rollers and the conveyor belt, which is a wear point. Volumetric sensors don't need contact, meaning that minor maintenance is expected. On the other hand, the system seems to suffer the presence of water reflections. We are testing the effect of reducing the speed of conveyor belts, by changing the pulleys. In this way water has more time to flow down and a reduction of this effect is expected.

For monitoring the precision of these sensors, a comparison is made between volumes read by the sensors and values obtained from GPS survey on stockpiles and sales volumes.

2.2.3 Pump liter counters

Pump liter counters are installed on the pipeline of the fresh extracted water and on the pipeline that supplies water to the plant. With these sensors it is possible to monitor fresh water usage and recirculating water fed to the plant to monitor and work on decreasing fresh water consumption.

Figure 19. Liter counter installed on recirculating water pipeline.

2.2.4 Pressure sensors

Pressure sensors are mounted on the top of water cyclones. Water cyclones are machine that separate fine material (sand) from dirty water exploiting centrifugal force. Installation of these sensors allows to control their performance, working on decreasing water consumption and increasing efficiency.

Figure 20. Pressure sensor mounted on two water cyclones.

2.2.5 Electric transducers

Electric transducers are placed in the electrical cabinet and detect current absorption of the crushers. Operators can thus monitor machines performances, decreasing energy consumption.

Figure 21. Current absorption of the machines in Pioltello plant monitored from Maestro's portal.

Electric transducers are placed in the electrical cabin monoblock and monitor two water pumps of the cyclones, three motors of the crushers, four vibrating screens and the pump of water purifier system.

Current absorption (shown in the figure below) is one of the key data for developing crushing optimization.

Figure 22. Current absorption of the main crusher.

2.2.6 Vibration sensors

Vibration sensors are mounted on the screens for sensing their motion. In this way, it is possible to regulate material flow so that the machine works more efficiently. Monitoring unexpected vibrations warn if the screener has been loaded too much material. The sensors measure vibrations the 3 directions and are applied.

Figure 23. Vibration sensor installed on the vibrating screen.

2.2.7 Cameras

Cameras are installed on strategic positions in the plant. The video output is shown on a monitor positioned in the quarry operator office. Even with an increase and development of the automation, still a visual monitoring remains important to ensure the plant is running with the most suitable parameters. For this reason, cameras monitor the tunnel extraction gates and the conveyor belt feeding the plant.

Figure 24. Video monitoring from quarry operator office (left). Camera installed on the conveyor belt (right).

2.2.8 Level sensors

Level sensors are positioned on the top of the two silos. Silos are used for storing the aggregates before been fed to the two crushers. Once the material is above a parametrized threshold, the crusher starts operating. In this way the level starts

decreasing. When the inferior threshold is reached, the crusher stops. In this way, it is ensured that the crusher works always with a continuous material supply and there is no interruption of material feeding. The material level inside the silos is detected with ultrasonic sensors and the instantaneous level is remotely monitored.

Figure 25. Level sensor (left) and Silo filling level measured by ultrasonic sensor (right).

2.2.9 Arco weighing system

Installation of weigh system has been performed on week 15-19 May. Weigh system supplied by ARCO has been installed on the conveyor belt placed immediately after the main cone crusher of the plant, which is the same where is placed one of the two PSD sensors. The sensor is composed by a triad of idle rollers mounted on a load-cell, for weigh measurement and by an idle spring-loaded wheel with an encoder sensor for speed detection.

Data are collected by a computer and stored locally. The communication system to data Lake has to be developed.

At the moment this data is sent to Data Lake manually, extracting data from the PC dedicated to the weighing bridge and then uploading it to the Data Lake.

This data is fundamental for the development of MINTEK’s crushing model because it directly measures the material flow going out the crusher.

Figure 26. Weigh system composed of (from left to right) weigh cellar, encoder and electrical cabinet with HMI.

Figure 27. Daily production [ton] passing through the weigh system.

2.3 Monitoring sensors and analysis tools + Recognition system for workers (Task 3.3)

Going towards the direction of the development of monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery in Loading, two cameras together with two sensor devices supplied by ABAUT have been installed on wheel loaders. These georeferenced devices collect very detailed information about the location and movement pattern of the machines and the cameras snap periodical photos of the working surroundings and of the shovel, which then get processed on the ABAUT servers. The users receive the results of the analysed data on the ABAUT portal, grouped under different topics, according to necessity.

In case of the Pioltello pilot site, the two main topics delivered by ABAUT are working data of the two wheel loaders and the recognition of workers nearby mobile heavy equipment for H&S purposes. Therefore, our focus with ABAUT and the data provided by their system is organized according to these two topics.

Working data of the wheel loaders

For monitoring the activities of the two wheel loaders, we have divided our plant into four areas of interest. In the ABAUT platform we can visualize how much time the machines spend in each of the areas, how often do they cross from one area to the other and what distance do they travel – for any selected time period (see Figure below). In addition to this, we can visualize the trajectories of the machines, get additional information about their speed and about idling events, displayed on the map of the site where also the four regions are visible, as all information is georeferenced.

Figure 28. Working data of the Wheel loaders on ABAUT's portal.

Due to the images collected by the cameras and together with the sensor data, it is possible to count the shovels of each wheel loader and also to detect the material mass flow – currently we are investigating this perspective together with ABAUT – we have defined new working areas that are associated to different product muckpiles and we are analysing the details of the mass flow.

All images collected from our site are organized according to location and time, and available in the ABAUT platform (see Figure 29).

Figure 29. Photo from wheel loader's camera taken from ABAUT's portal.

Recognition of workers nearby mobile heavy equipment

Another important feature of this implementation is the recognition system for workers, which detects the presence of a pedestrian in proximity of the vehicle. This feature is the basis for the development of a recognition system for workers nearby mobile machinery and H&S systems for mobile equipment. The risk-event detected by the camera is geolocated on the site map, so that a risk-map is built from this data. It is thus possible to study in which area human-vehicle interactions are more frequent and it is easier to take precautions.

The idea of the monitoring system is to analyse the path and roads via the mobile camera installed in the machine for identifying hazardous situations with the workers in the surroundings of the mobile equipment.

The worker is recognized automatically by the system and the person is blurred according GDPR. The system helps to recognize hazard activities and to perform according to the indicators, new safety trainings or safety directives.

Features:

- Identification of the worker in the machinery surrounding according to a defined period of time [e.g., daily, weekly, monthly].
- Location and time of the picture in a map application.
- Speed of the machine in the moment of the recognition.
- Places of maximum frequency.

Figure 30. Risk map of Pioltello site.

Figure 31. Wheel loader traffic map and workers identification pictures

Figure 32. Details of recognition of workers around mobile heavy machines.

All the information is accessible, from any device, at ABAUT's Analytics Platform.

The information can be sorted by day, machinery or area according to the user. In addition, it is possible to integrate different information from the mobile heavy machinery such as mass flow, idle time or machinery utilization.

Going towards the direction of the development of monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery in Loading, two cameras supplied by ABAUT have been installed on wheel loaders.

Figure 33. Wheel loaders where the two cameras have been installed.

Figure 34. Cameras mounted on the two wheel loaders in Pioltello site.

These georeferenced devices snap periodical photos of the shovel which then get processed. From ABAUT's portal it is possible to consult working data of the two-wheel loaders. The plant is virtually divided in four areas, then the system counts passages, time spent, and distance travelled in each zone. In addition, the path of the vehicles is visible on a map and also idle status positions and shovel counts.

Another important feature of this implementation is the recognition system for workers, which detects the presence of a pedestrian in proximity of the vehicle. This feature is the basis for the development of a recognition system for workers nearby mobile machinery and H&S systems for mobile equipment. The risk-event detected by the camera is geo-located

on the site map, so that a risk-map is built from this data. It is thus possible to study in which area human-vehicle interactions are more frequent and it is easier to take precautions.

Figure 35. Risk map of Pioltello site.

2.4 Platform design implementation (Task 4.2)

Meetings have performed with AKKODIS and Ma-estro for supporting platform design implementation and defining the format in which the data are transmitted to DATA LAKE.

The PLC constantly communicates with the DATA LAKE sending strings containing most of the data accessible from the Scada system.

Actions	ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process	Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for HOLCIM	11/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	27/03/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	30/03/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	30/03/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	03/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	03/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	03/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	03/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	04/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	05/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	01/05/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	14	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	13	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	15	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	20	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	19	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	18	Treatment (KTA2.1)	Automation-Process Control	Maestro	String	15/06/2023

Figure 36. List of files uploaded to DATA LAKE from Pioltello's plant PLC.

2.5 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)

HOLCIM supported SIGMA and UPM-AI in obtaining data for stockpile volume estimation. This service has been designed to test four different techniques, each with specific needs and advantages over the others. Satellite images of the pilot's stockpiles have been obtained from the European Space Agency (ESA). HOLCIM supported SIGMA and UPM-AI with drone flight video shooting during visiting days at Pioltello pilot site and with camera testing. During these visiting days, three cameras were placed and moved around the site, collecting video footage on three stockpiles.

Figure 37. Pioltello plant from drone flight.

Drone flights are regarded as part of the state-of-the-art for 3D reconstruction and volume computation in deployment conditions similar to pilot sites. Unfortunately, in the DEQ project, it has been identified that drone flights suffer from significant limitations due to the costs and training of specialized personnel. Additionally, multiple sites throughout Europe are located where drone flights are prevented by the law or local authorities. Thus, alternative approaches need to be developed, while this information, including that collected at HOLCIM, can be used as a ground truth during tests and validation of alternative technologies.

Figure 38. Pioltello stockpile volumes reconstruction and volume computation.

Fixed cameras are considered to be an alternative approach. Triangulation techniques have been in the scientific literature for years but are very demanding regarding image quality and position control. Additionally, fixed cameras also allow the capture of video footage on the sites that could help other services (risk prevention, etc.). Nonetheless, hardware and installation costs certainly impact this technology, depending on the camera's requirements for resolution and quality, the coverage (number of cameras), etc. Tests at Pioltello allowed DEQ researchers to evaluate this alternative, considering all the elements involved. Researchers reconstructed one of the piles and validated the distances to the piles and other requirements for the cameras and the setup. This same approach was validated in Fenouillet (Granulats VICAT), where adaptations to the reconstruction protocol allowed the complete reconstruction of the piles from all camera views.

Alternatively, moving cameras could collect video footage to reconstruct piles and compute volumes. This approach may require more video footage than the previous one but does not require a fixed installation (may operate on smartphones), does not require calibration after installation, and is not affected by spurious events, such as an uncontrolled change in the location, orientation or viewpoint of the cameras. It could be based on standard hardware, such as smartphones. This approach has been tested outside the pilot sites for initial validation, but also at CEMEX-Valdilecha, coordinated by Sigma and UPM-AI, VICAT (coordinated by UPM-AI) and CEMEX. There Sigma and UPM-AI used a set of mobile applications that had to be tested. UPM-AI and SIGMA prepared some guidelines, and HOLCIM supported both teams by recording videos around stockpiles attending to these specifications. A video application runs in parallel with a Sensor Logger, which acquires other data, including GPS positioning, acceleration, orientation, etc. This acquisition setup is a prototype that needs to be validated. The additional information helps in the reconstruction process, the extraction of the floor, and the computation of the actual volume, among several others.

Finally, satellite imagery poses several challenges to computing stockpile volume due to the lack of information regarding height (which is now being researched), the limited resolution of satellite imagery (new satellite constellations may overcome this limitation), and the costs to acquire this data (being evaluated for the future service, currently being covered as part of a side project with ESA), among several others. Researchers of the DEQ project are using ground truth data collected at Pioltello to serve as a reference for AI algorithms being developed to reconstruct the stockpile volumes.

Figure 39. Screenshots of Sensor Logger app and smartphone video of the stockpiles.

Tests on the reconstructed volumes suggest that volume computation error should be below 5%. Work is still being conducted to validate that the APP runs smoothly, that the data sharing is simple enough for users, that collected data can effectively be used in the reconstruction and the volume computation, and that precision is below the given threshold.

The current approach has validated the use of smartphone videos. This new approach has also been tested at HOLCIM, following the guidelines and tools by Sigma and UPM-AI. The acquisition process based on smartphones is to be validated to ease data collection and submission to the data platforms. The apps to be used have been reevaluated to ease the video footage recording and avoid needing to (re)configure the acquisition conditions in the smartphones.

The following figure summarizes the dataset that have been collected, including a sample of the images collected, and a view on the 3D model that was reconstructed. Further and detailed information can be found in Section 3.3 of Deliverable 4.3 (Report on the AI Algorithms and Services).

Figure 40. Sample images and 3D reconstructions of stockpiles from the different sites.

Finally, HOLCIM also supported Sigma and UPM-AI in collecting sound and vibration records of conveyor belts and screens for the site at Pioltello to validate their approach toward the predictive maintenance AI service. These were the first audio and vibration records collected within the project for preliminary tests and the audios. Sigma and UPM-AI have validated these audios and have been working with instrumentation equipment to collect additional audio records at the CEMEX and VICAT pilot sites. The Sigma and UPM-AI are using these to build Artificial Intelligence models that describe how the different parts of the production plant operate (belts, crusher, screens, etc.). Further and detailed information can be found in Section 3.5 of Deliverable 4.3 (Report on the AI Algorithms and Services)

Some of these data were incorporated in research publications, presented at the 53 International Conference of Acoustic Technologies and at the XV International Congress on Energy and Raw Materials.

2.6 BIM (Task 4.4)

Photos of Pioltello pilot site have been sent to APP, together with information regarding plant assets, plant flowchart and a scheme of static and dynamic data that are important for us to access.

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is the methodology for creating and managing information on engineering and construction projects across the project lifecycle. Within APP works, their main goals were the following:

1. Model Development: It was developed based on information shared with APP and WP1 data, to be used in the rest of APP's subtasks.

Figure 41. BIM model of Pioltello plant.

Figure 42. Top view of BIM model.

2. Common Data Environment (CDE) Development: It is a digital repository that allows to virtually navigate through the plant, interacting with the different assets (e.g. screens, crushers, conveyor belts). Each single assets contains static data like manuals, spare parts list and technical specifications but also dynamic data, for example electrical consumption, production rate and other information acquired by installed sensors, thanks to the data exchange with Data Lake.

Figure 43. Selection menu of the BIM model.

- 4D BIM Planning: It is a planning method that consists in integrating the quarry schedule and planning information with the 3D model to visualize the activities planned, help analyse possible issues or implement improvements prior to its development. In this case, a long-term planning was developed by APP to show how it would be useful to see the complete progress of the site, from its preparation activities to its restoration phase.

Figure 44. 4D BIM planning

Figure 45. 4D BIM model of the plant.

2.7 Environmental Performance based on Historical Data (Task 5.4)

For each site, the environmental performance in over 30 environmental impact categories has been calculated using historical data from 2019. A model of the plant has been built in the online web platform, *PlantSmith*, where all products have been connected to consumption data for the year 2019. Background environmental models have then been used to estimate the environmental performance of each product group. The results have been presented in Deliverable 5.4 for the sites.

Figure 46. Environmental performance simulation

3 Results

The installation of two PSD (Particle Size Detection) sensors for the measurement of granulometry before and after the cone crusher is an important step forward in Crushing and Screening Optimization. Together with the supply of aggregates samples to MINTEK and with the share of process information and parameters, this analysis is bringing a deeper understanding of the process, developing a Remote Crushing and Screening Interface (RCSI) and improving KPIs related to it by making more efficient the crushing.

A fundamental point for monitoring and estimating the achieved results is get sufficient data for the calculation of KPIs and also making sure that these data are reliable and actually representative of the status of the processes.

With the installation of sensors and information exchange with Data Lake a wide variety of information are available. The most important data are production volumes of each product, and of the raw material fed to the plant. Then there are electrical absorptions of crushers, vibrating screens and main water pumps, but also the number of interferences of wheel loaders with pedestrians, fresh and recycled water consumption, stockpile volumes, measurements of vibrations of the screen. In addition, time information is supplied, as the starting and stop times of the plant and of the different machines (crushers and screens).

With this set of data, it is possible to calculate and monitor KPIs. Reaching a precise definition of the KPIs is important, so that it is possible and reliable to obtain the data for KPIs calculation and the KPI effectively allows to monitor the performance studied. In particular, the table below expresses the KPIs that have been defined for Pioltello pilot site.

Table 2 Specific KPIs for Pioltello pilot site.

KPI	Description	Units	Frequency
Energy absorption	Energy consumed to process a ton of material (total processed material)	kWh/ton	system
Total saleable materials	Total saleable materials produced for a certain day	ton, mc	system
Water management - Fresh water	Counter litre on the well pump	Liter/ton	day
Water management - Recycling water	Counter litre on the recycling pipe line	%	day
REE	Plant productivity	%	monthly
Crushing efficiency index	kWh/ton predicted for the predicted amount of fines	kWh/ton	
Stocks level (by mobile o satellite)	Total amount of every saleable product	mc	monthly
Interference index	Interference wheel loader /pedestrian in an area	number	day

1.3.1 To the previous table of KPIs specific to Pioltello plant, also general KPIs are added, which are valid for all the pilot sites:

Table 3 General KPIs valid for all pilot sites.

Ref. N.	KPI	Description	Units
1	Hourly production	Production processed per hour	ton/h
2	Daily production	Total gross production per day (rolling)	ton
3	Hourly production rate	Actual hourly production / Plant BDP	%

Selecting between the KPIs above, below here there are two examples of KPIs monitored over time.

Figure 47. Monthly average hourly production (ton/h) of Pioltello plant. In blue is reported the trending line.

Figure 48. Monthly Running Equipment Effectiveness (REE) of the plant. In blue is reported the trending line.

3.1 Impact assessment

Regarding the impacts that the project is having on Pioltello pilot site, the most important aspect that emerges right from the first stages is the monitoring of the production process. Sensors and AI algorithms are permitting to reach a high level of control and awareness of the production processes. Between all, two of the most worthwhile applications are the PSD sensors, that allow to understand the behaviour of the crushing process and the size distributions of the aggregates before and after the crushing. Then also volumetric sensor and weighbridge system have an interesting impact because they measure the production of the different final products and of the crushed aggregates, thus allowing a remote control and monitoring of the main production parameters.

A determining impact on safety then, comes from installation of georeferenced cameras on wheel loaders, which permit to create a risk map of the interactions between pedestrians and wheel loaders.

As a summary of the effort, research & developments and studies invested in the project, we expect to measure and analyse the results comparing with the targets (monitored by the KPIs) estimated at the beginning of the project especially focused on energy consumption reduction (compared with referred year 2019), increase the efficiency of the plant and reduction of fresh water consumption and increasing recycled water. Another important target is related to the increase of the level of H&S performances related to interaction between heavy machinery and workers.

4 Future

Concerning the task 6.3, an important further step is the implementation of the communication between liter counters, already installed, with SCADA system so that it possible to monitor fresh water and recycled water for a better control of the process.

Also with ARCO weighing system, a communication with SCADA system has to be implemented in next period, then connected with MINTEK's crushing system.

At the meantime we will proceed with the progression of data acquisition regarding Pioltello pilot site's process parameters and the creation of a history database.

Then, thanks to the data acquired from the sensors installed until now, the evolution of KPIs values is being monitored, expecting a gradual improvement as consequence of the development and implementation of the technologies and solutions researched from the other partners of the project which have the scope of increasing efficiency and productivity. At the moment, all the sensors included by the project have been installed. For a few of them still a communication needs to be implemented in the system.

An improvement is expected in energy consumption, efficiency, productivity, freshwater consumption and safety level. Improvements are expected to come from model for crushing and screening optimization, enhancements are foreseen also from production control system and automation, recognition system for workers, AI algorithms and Building Information Modelling (BIM).

An important shortcoming found during the implementation regards the volumetric sensors (see chapter 2.2.2). If it will not be possible to reach an acceptable degree of precision with this technology (error below 5%), other technologies could be evaluated.

Then regarding the research on new methodologies for stockpiles volume calculation (see chapter 2.5), it is expected to determine which of the alternatives evaluated is the most suitable for this application.

5 Conclusions

Pioltello pilot site's activities up to this point have mainly consisted in supporting and implementing technologies, solutions and research in collaborations with the other partners of the project. As pilot site it has been fundamental to share our know-how and a deep understanding of the processes, thus communicating the needs from productive and operative point of view and identifying where there is a margin for improvement and the directions for enhancing the KPIs.

The first fundamental step for improving production performances (improving KPIs) is to acquire sufficient data for better monitoring the processes thus having sufficient information also to calculate KPIs and estimate the evolution of performances. Sensors have been installed, connected with PLC and data is sent to Data Lake, then to DWH so that data are extracted and shown in the dashboard for being simply visualized.

it is possible to study in detail process performances. The information sent to Data Lake are fundamental parameters such as production volumes for each type of product, electrical absorption of crushers, vibrating screens and main water pumps, but also the number of interferences of wheel loaders with pedestrians, fresh and recycled water consumption, PSD (particle size distribution) in 2 points, stockpile volumes, vibrations of the screen.

Once the installation of the sensors has been concluded, a testing phase enabled a fine tune of the applications. After that, a more and more structured and consisting of database is getting populated, representing a data history, which is important because allows to observe and monitor the plant performance through a wider time period where there are external factors with a relevant impact on KPIs (e.g. environmental/weather conditions and changes in input material).

As explained more in detail in the previous chapter, in the next months it is expected to go through some important steps such as: determining the technology for stockpiles volume calculation, monitor KPIs and develop a Remote Crushing and Screening Interface (RCSI) and a Local Crushing and Screening Interface (LCSI).

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ANNEX I (Pioltello plant flowsheet diagram)

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